

METHODS OF FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF PATRIOTISM IN STUDENTS OF MILITARY HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6025412>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 15-december 2021

Accepted: 15-january 2022

Online: 5-february 2022

KEY WORDS

Patriotism, military education, loyalty to the country, military oath, laws, military knowledge, spirituality, armed forces.

ABSTRACT

Since the independence of the Uzbek people, in the system of spiritual and moral education of our youth, including students of military education, there is a sense of patriotism, faith in the motherland, patriotism, humanity and kindness. The formation of their feelings, their upbringing as loyal children of their people and homeland is becoming the spirituality and content of our lives. Patriotism is one of the most ancient and centuries-old human emotions, which has always had a specific social and psychological content and originality. As a result, national and universal values of patriotism emerged.

Our first President I.A.Karimov said, "Indeed, the feeling of homeland, the concept of homeland, must be as pure and great for us as a shrine. We must learn the great human virtue of honouring the motherland, protecting it from evil eyes and actions, and, if necessary, sacrificing our lives for our motherland. " Emphasizing that the great task facing teachers and intellectuals today is to bring up well-rounded, well-educated young people who have a deep sense of love for their country and motherland, devotion to the motherland and people, patriotism and humanity. "First of all, it is both a duty and an obligation to bring up our children, the younger generation, who are our support and hope, in the spirit of the Fatherland and the sense of humanity and purpose," he said. Therefore, it is a priority to develop a sense of patriotism in the minds of the younger generation.

Man's spiritual maturity is determined by the values that emerge, are formed and determine the spirituality of the individual, based on the formation of the values of patriotism, humanity and kindness in him. The future of independent Uzbekistan largely depends on the upbringing of a harmoniously developed generation. To do this, we must follow the noble ideas of our wise people and thinkers and teach our military youth the most popular moral values and values used by our ancestors from childhood in the educational process. The results of scientific research conducted by pedagogues and psychologists, as well as a number of initiatives of the Government of Uzbekistan, personally initiated and led by the first President Islam Karimov, in the interests of our children and people, such as human personality and upbringing, family

upbringing, healthy generation, documents and decisions were made.

In all spheres of life, based on the national interests of the republic, taking into account the age-old way of life, traditions, customs and skills of our ancestors, to form in our children feelings of love and sincerity for their homeland and people, application to the theory and practice of education is becoming one of the important urgent tasks.

According to the ancient Greek philosopher (384-322 BC) Aristotle, "it is not the goal but the means to achieve it that are decisive."

In epic narratives, which are considered to be our spiritual heritage, including the Avesto, Gorogly, Alpomish epics, Firdavsi's "Shohnoma", Mahmud Kashgari's "Devonu lug'atit-turk", and a number of other works consider the qualities of our ancestors as love of country, people, honour and loyalty to friends as their main social qualities.

The scholars of the first period of the Eastern revival (9th-11th centuries) were brought up in the tenets of Islam, tested them several times in life, and tried to convey them to us through words of wisdom. In particular, Abu Rayhan al-Beruni said, "The main cause of all vices is ignorance." Abu Ali ibn Sina said, "To know the truth, one must have knowledge, but any knowledge does not lead to the truth. To know the truth of one's knowledge, one must know logic." Medieval Central Asian scholars and 19th-century Jadids also focused on human qualities, highlighting the basic characteristics of a perfect human figure. In the works of thinkers, scientists, poets and sages of this period, human qualities that are important for social development - humanity, belief in knowledge, protection of the interests of the people, raising spirituality, achieving a

perfect man and a mature community - are highlighted.

The great thinkers and scholars of the East have devoted all their creative activity to the formation and development of the spiritual culture of the individual. This is the feature that distinguishes the creative activity of Eastern thinkers from that of Western thinkers. For example, in AlisherNavoi's epic "Farhod and Shirin" there is a strong desire to enjoy the source of courage, honesty, enlightenment, hard work, respect for the elderly, the interests of the state and the people. Human qualities such as self-interest, as well as loyal love, are embodied and can serve as an example for students of military education. In this way, the poet tried to show the basics of the formation and development of the spiritual culture of the individual. When Farhod is given the opportunity to run the country, he says that he is still young, that he has no experience in this field, and that it would be better if he was hired by people who are older than him and have more experience in public administration. will not accept this offer. However, Farhod was well-known among the courtiers and the common people for his knowledge and skills in this area. With this behaviour of the poet Farhod, he tried to show the following qualities that develop spiritual culture:

1. Ability to self-evaluate and have a deep sense of responsibility for each task.
2. Take things in stride and try not focus too much on the problem.
3. Respect older and more experienced people and try to learn from their experience.
4. Stay away from the flaws of bureaucracy. Amir Temur also gave a lot of educational instructions in his charters. In

particular, he stressed the need to treat public administration with justice, to treat the intelligentsia fairly, to show compassion to the poor, and to defend national values in a sustainable manner. Thoughts are of great importance in the formation of a direct spiritual culture.

Farobi's "City of Noble People" discusses the problem of enforcing laws, which is one of the main criteria of democracy. According to Farobi, when a new law is passed, a true legislator will take into account the fact that it will bring happiness, joy, freedom and prosperity to all classes, generations and people of the country. The law should be well-received by people with a variety of personalities and qualities.

According to Farobi, happiness can be achieved through wisdom and constant striving. Therefore, the law only leads to prosperity when it is focused on cultivating a strong spirit and common sense. This means that the leader must strive to educate the people, to strengthen their spirit and understanding. If we summarize and organize these positive qualities, which are the human criteria of our ancient ancestors and are required of everyone, the following system of social qualities is embodied: first - courage, then - knowledge, resourcefulness, patriotism, diligence, humanity, morality and decency, friendship, thrift, and frugality. Both religious and secular works played an important role in the formation of such qualities.

The lofty ideals of the perfect man are especially deeply expressed in the works of thinkers such as Abu Nasr al-Farabi and AlisherNavoi. In fact, a perfect human being is a high position that can be attained through teachings and practices.

E. Yusupov in his work "Spiritual foundations of human perfection" said that:

Spirituality is the spirituality of man, the stages of its formation, the factors that play a special role in the formation of spirituality, the social development of spirituality, moral significance, as well as the conditions for the formation of his spirituality, based on the psychological characteristics of the individual. Emphasis is placed on the fact that patriotism is a characteristic of a person with a high level of spirituality. The concept of "patriotism" is also interpreted. According to the author, "patriotism is a characteristic of all people who connect their destiny with the destiny of the homeland and the nation. The opportunities, glory and prestige of the nation's development also depend on the level of formation of patriotic values in the people of this nation. "In his book "Pride" M.Sharifkhodjaev expressed his views on the values of rightful pride in the great state of the future, the achievements of the republic during the years of independence. Focusing on faith and patriotism, the author emphasizes the need for a thorough study of the history of the Uzbek people, the restoration of national traditions and customs, enriching it with modern achievements, explaining to the military youth on the basis of modern requirements. .

B.Aminov, T.Rasulov in their book "Homeland - a jewel in the heart" to form national and patriotic values in students in the spirit of devotion to the Motherland, faith, ancestral heritage, devotion to the teachings provided training materials on As the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan I.A.Karimov said: "Uzbekistan is a sacred Motherland, the land of our ancestors. We are glad that raising our children in the spirit of devotion to this land, instilling in their hearts a loving love for every age of this blessed land - is

becoming one of the most important qualities of today. In his speeches and works, the First President of Uzbekistan I.A.Karimov lamented that in the spirituality of our people, in the hearts of our people, a citizen living on the land where he lives, if necessary, will not spare his life, to form love for the Motherland from an early age. "First of all, it is both a duty and an obligation to bring up our children, our young generation, who are our support and hope, our hope and future, in the way of the Motherland and the patriotic feeling and purpose," he said.

Doctor of Psychological Sciences, Professor Z. Nishonova defines the concept of "harmoniously developed person" as follows: "A fully developed person is a person who is able to express himself, his abilities in all respects, mentally mature, highly talented and capable." He is a free, creative person, who is spiritually high, morally pure, physically healthy that able to feel the beauty of life. The author reveals the role of spiritual and moral views put forward by Eastern thinkers in the history of the formation of the perfect man and their significance for today, which serves as an important guide for the effective organization of spiritual and moral education in educational institutions. The concepts of national "pride" and "pride" in the formation of patriotic values in the psychological literature can reflect both individual and social characteristics in terms of the object of study. After all, personal pride is a psychological trait that is unique to a person, such as his or her social status (e.g., status as a member of a particular nation), personal characteristics, lifestyle, professional or social activity, and satisfaction with accomplishments is considered to form. Having the values of national pride means understanding, being

proud and satisfied with the place of a person of a certain nation in the world community, his position, his contribution to human development and civilization.

Patriotism is a sense of belonging to a particular nation and a sense of pride in the contribution of that nation to world culture, as well as a sense of devotion to one's own nation and practical action in that direction. S. Ochilov's book "Spirituality and Fundamentals of Education" describes the reforms taking place in Uzbekistan during the period of independence, the educational process. The author puts forward the following opinion: "Education means the game, the home. In the process of their work, in the study of education and science, it is necessary to understand and know the political explanation of life and life lessons, as well as the state of personal example. These factors must be combined ", he says. According to him, "Man should be educated in two main ways: by the direct influence of others, that is, by teaching, as well as by reading the thoughts, teachings, and works of the sages, so that students can express their thoughts, people in his actions, in what he has done, and in what he is doing, he is able to draw appropriate conclusions - the most powerful - can be nurtured through thinking. Our first president notes that it is advisable to recommend this set of studied samples as an educational guide and guide for young military students. The formation of patriotic values of military youth is not limited to theoretical knowledge. Only selfless young people, who serve the country, the nation, and protect its interests, care about its future. In the future, young professionals working in the socio-political, economic, legal and other spheres of our country will be formed on the basis of their social activity,

the deeper the patriotic values in their minds and worldviews. The Republican psychologists' research on spirituality analyzes national values and its methods and tools for the development of military students. Educating military students is one of the main tasks of military school teachers. With the help of upbringing, the tried, best, progressive experience of generations is assimilated and passed on to the new generation, people's consciousness and moral values are inculcated in this society, and a conscious attitude towards them is formed. Therefore, one of the important tasks of the education system is to form and develop the values of faith and patriotism in the worldview of adolescent students, to turn them into sustainable beliefs.

It is important to have a deeper understanding of the essence of independence, to love and be proud of the Motherland, to inculcate in the educational process what military students should pay attention to in order to protect the honour of the Motherland. From the content of the sources discussed above, it is clear that the coverage of the content, methods, forms and means of the formation of beliefs and patriotic values in military students is an urgent problem in psychology. Z. Kurbaniyazova, who conducted research on the formation of patriotic values in adolescents, including military students, along with the understanding of national identity, the essence of their values, puts forward the following opinion about the components of this value: Understanding is the beginning of all human qualities, the achievement of a solid unity of knowledge, skills and abilities about the historical memory, socio-spiritual life, national heritage, customs and traditions, values, psyche of our people, their conscious

assessment, achieving positive spiritual values, conscious self-management, living with the values of the Motherland, contributing to its development; it is a combination of qualities such as respect for one's mother tongue and respect for other nations. It allows teenagers to learn about national identity, the past of the nation, the uniqueness of its history. Because a person who does not understand the history of his people cannot determine his place in society and his position among different nations. A person who does not have a social status cannot think independently and make decisions in different situations. Therefore, he is doomed to dependence, servitude and slavery. In the process of forming patriotic values in adolescent military students, it instills in them a sense of confidence in the future, making forward-looking plans and aspirations. Confidence in the future nurtures in a person mental endurance, the formation and manifestation of willpower, motivates him to try to get out of the situation on the basis of logical thinking, even in complex, very difficult situations. In the formation of patriotic values, national customs, traditions and values, the ideas put forward in them, serve to form the human psyche, in which to cultivate spiritual and moral qualities. One of the defining factors of nationality is customs, traditions and values. Therefore, as a representative of the nation, the preservation and enrichment of national traditions, customs and values is becoming a social and psychological necessity. In turn, pride in the fact that the ideas of national customs, traditions and values serve the development of the nation, the development of humanity, ensures that adolescent military students acquire the values of faith and patriotism.

In the organization of educational work, it is desirable to pay attention to the training of military students in the skills of preserving national traditions, customs and values, the ability to strive to enrich them. It is advisable to pay special attention to introducing military students to the heroes of our time, who are effective in the field of production and creativity, and to be active in this direction. It is necessary to create psychological and pedagogical conditions for adolescents not to put personal interests above the interests of society, to fully understand their human duties to society and the nation, to strive to work for the happiness of the people and the welfare of the country.

It is necessary to revive the tradition of organizing large-scale and high-level interesting events promoting patriotic ideas among students studying in the military.

To achieve a holistic study of the psychological, pedagogical and philosophical aspects of the formation of patriotic values in them, to adequately study the effective ways, factors and means of organizing this process. Hence, it is important to ensure that adolescents acquire patriotic values and to organize the process as a whole, in which the targeted use of each effective factor, the ability to see opportunities and evaluate their effectiveness.

As in any field, there are significant changes in the training of military personnel. Demands for military officers and sergeants are growing. Because the current officer and sergeant is not only a narrow-minded specialist with limited knowledge in a particular field, but also a person with deep intellectual ability, broad-minded, highly cultured and spiritual, with his own knowledge, personal

example there must be an educator who can educate and train his subordinates. "Military personnel," said the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan in his congratulatory message to the Defenders of the Motherland on the occasion of the 21st anniversary of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan, "first of all, have deep knowledge and modern thinking, intellectual maturity." Radical improvement of the system of training officers, as well as highly qualified junior commanders-sergeants, who form the core of our army today, should also be one of the most important areas of the Armed Forces Command reflecting the main trends in the development of the military sphere and martial arts, taking into account the foreign experience, forms and methods of conducting warfare in fundamentally new specialties and areas of science. It is no exaggeration to say that training is the most responsible aspect of the work ahead of us. "As in any field, there have been great positive changes in the training of military personnel. Demand for military personnel is growing. Because the current officer is not only a narrow-minded specialist with limited knowledge in a particular field, but also a person with deep intellectual potential, broad-minded, highly cultured and spiritual, with his own knowledge, personal example it must be a capable and skilled educator who can educate and train his subordinates. What knowledge, skills and competencies should military listeners, especially educators, have in military education, what should they do, how should they behave and what should they pay attention to? To a certain extent, pedagogical sciences answer these and other similar questions. This course aims to shed light on the content of military

pedagogical skills, its components and ways of revealing and shaping their specific features.

Regarding the types of military service, the following should be mentioned:

Military service is a special type of public service of citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the ranks of the Armed Forces in the performance of general military service.

- The following types of military service will be introduced:
 1. conscription;
 2. military service in the mobilization reserve;
 3. contract
 4. military service;

Service of reservists who have served in the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan for peacetime military service in peacetime as soldiers and sergeants, as well as for service in the mobilization reserve, the Armed Forces from eighteen to twenty-seven years, depending on health. The purpose of legal education is to improve the legal culture of the younger generation, the development of legal knowledge of citizens and the rule of law, obedience to the law, patriotism, humanity, national independence. The main goal is to bring up in the spirit of the idea. Uzbekistan is a country with a great future. The education of the perfect man has always been one of the most topical issues. Legal education of young people plays an important role in building the rule of law and a free civil society. Legal education plays a key role in educating young people in the spirit of humanity, patriotism and the idea of national independence, as well as in raising their legal knowledge. In the legal education and upbringing of young people, our national traditions, customs it is known that if we are able to form a spirit

of love and devotion to our heritage, it is the product of our work, which has a positive effect on each of us adequate legal training is required. However, the concept of legal education and its explanatory methods have not been fully covered by our scientists so far. Legal education can be seen in a broad and narrow sense. In a broad sense, it is an education aimed at influencing the minds of the whole community, and in the narrow sense, it is a way of influencing the mind of an individual. As a result of legal education, if the general public or a person understands the legitimacy of their actions, tries to avoid violating the law and order, and is able to govern himself consciously and in accordance with the rule of law, the goal is achieved. Thus, legal education is an organized, systematic, goal-oriented activity that can influence an individual's "group of individuals" and develop in them the qualities of legal awareness, legal knowledge, and obedience to the law.

Of course, in order to follow the law, you must first know it. Through legal education, it is necessary to inform everyone about what can and cannot be done, what society and the state require of them. Among the violators is the illegality of their actions. It is common not to understand, not to think that it is illegal, and not to think that such an action is not punishable. In order not to create such an understanding, it is necessary to explain and explain that in the process of legal education in each community there is a violation of the established order, non-compliance with the law, disciplinary, administrative, material or criminal penalties. Special attention has been paid to the strengthening of education since the sixties. It should be noted that at that time,

legal education is still closely linked with education.

The main directions of military education are physical and spiritual upbringing of the younger generation in the spirit of patriotism, preparation of young people of pre-conscription and conscription age for state labour and defence. Military knowledge includes mastering the required amount, physical training, studying the military history, symbols and principles of one's homeland, forming a patriotic citizen, a loyal warrior.

During military training, students should learn:

- to understand their constitutional rights and obligations, to know the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the defence of the Motherland and its protection from armed aggression;
- The military doctrine of the Republic of Uzbekistan is focused on defence, duties of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan and other troops;
- Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Defence" "On General Military Obligation and Military Service", Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the organization of service of citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan". To study the main provisions of the Resolution "On military registration and expulsion of citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan, criminal and administrative liability for war crimes and refusal to serve in the military":
 - Study and understand the basic requirements of the Charter of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the military oath;
 - Familiarity with the weapons and military equipment of the military unit, the understanding and location of personnel;

- have the basics of military work, the necessary military knowledge and practical skills, as well as physical fitness and mental and spiritual strength;

- will master the basics of civil protection and medical knowledge.

Storytelling, conversation, and explanatory techniques are used to explore areas of the military establishment that are not related to practical action, and the explanation is done using posters, slides, and educational films. The actions of the group guard are practically studied in a specially equipped place. In order to help students consciously master the charter, it is advisable to create conditions for independent work with the charter during the lessons. It is noteworthy that the program includes a new topic "The right to armed conflict" in the section on the basics of military service. The fact is that the Republic of Uzbekistan acceded to the Geneva Conventions of 1949 and Additional Protocols of 1977 in September 1993. Article 19 of the Charter of the Internal Service of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan stipulates that every serviceman must know and follow the international rules of treatment of non-military population in the places of hostilities, as well as the military age. As noted in the preamble, this means that Uzbekistan recognizes the "supremacy of universally recognized rules of international law." The inclusion of the four-hour topic "Law of Armed Conflict" in the curriculum of military law for young people is one of the manifestations of the Republic of Uzbekistan's responsible approach to the implementation of international agreements. In connection with the introduction of the four-hour theme "Law of Armed Conflict" in the Republic of Uzbekistan - Undergraduate

students studying in the field of military education and the current military leader (Military Vocational Education Law) There is a need to increase the knowledge and skills of teachers on the topic of "The right to armed conflict" and to further improve their methodological skills.

Currently, the subject of "Law of Armed Conflict" is taught in accordance with the approved curriculum for undergraduate students studying in the field of compulsory military education, based on the curriculum, the text of lectures have been developed. Perspective plans have been developed to further improve and develop the teaching of the subject of "Law of Armed Conflict". At the same time, at the current stage of reforming the military education system, the requirements for the professional level of military teachers are growing. the role of personal responsibility for outcomes is growing. A teacher-practitioner-psychologist should replace a science teacher who knows his subject well, knows the cadet's personality well and knows how to manage himself, develop and educate students.

This can be achieved not only by a teacher who has no knowledge of the subject being taught, but also by a teacher who is able to apply psychological and pedagogical laws in practice to master them. At the same time, in traditional military universities, fundamental scientific training is conducted by specialists who know their job well, but are not ready for pedagogical activity. Many, and not just elementary teachers, were ready to address seemingly simple issues of pedagogical activity. Most of them are committed to the template, the monotonous methods of teaching, are limited by some practical skills that allow them to conduct lessons, and are fully

convinced that this is sufficient for pedagogical activity.

It is believed that among this part of the teachers, it is sufficient to know the subject of specialization for the teaching activity. In many ways, the formation of these military teachers is mainly related to working on the content of the subject being taught (supplementing knowledge about it, including them in a lecture course, etc). The formation of a teacher is, as a rule, based on the personal, personal experience of teaching 10-15 years or even 20 years ago: "I teach as I teach." The model of reproductive-communicative education is repeated, which is based on informing the cadets about the "knowledge" completed outside the preparatory activity. The trainee is obliged to receive the contact information, then memorize it, and then, as a rule, repeat it orally. The results of such teaching are well known: a negative attitude towards mastering the theory of teaching has a negative impact on the process of teacher training and the quality of teaching.

At the beginning of the training, the facilitator noted that the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Defence" was adopted on July 3, 1992, and in May 2001, amendments and additions were made to it. It announces that the edition has been approved. It then provides information on the content of the law. The second article of the law states that the defence of the Republic of Uzbekistan is a set of political, economic, military, social and legal measures aimed at protecting the state sovereignty, territorial integrity, views of the republic and the peaceful life of the population. The main principles of state policy in the field of defence are as follows; except for the cases of non-use of military force against another state, prevention and

repulsion of aggression, as well as assistance of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the states bound by the relevant treaties; participation in collective security systems in accordance with international law; non-participation in military-political blocs; the similarity of military construction to the nature of modern wars and armaments; denial of production, processing, acquisition, distribution and deployment of nuclear and other types of weapons of mass destruction; adequacy of defence; ensuring that military service is honourable. While explaining the articles and principles of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Defence" to the students, it is important that the facilitator gives real-life examples of the application of the link. After explaining the content of the lesson, the facilitator is encouraged to invite the students for an interview, ask questions and increase their activity.

Introduce students to the general responsibilities of military personnel, giving them an understanding of commanders and subordinates, adults and juniors, familiarization with the rights and responsibilities of direct and indirect managers. They develop the skills to comply with the requirements of the statute. The analysis shows that in recent years, ideas about the essence of the professional and pedagogical culture of a military teacher have become a universal feature and a professional feature in the encyclopedia. In this context, the problem of improving the professional and pedagogical skills of a military teacher is not only an objective social need, but also a subjective need to improve the professional skills of a military teacher. The teacher selection system is obscure and steeped in outdated stereotypes that have a serious impact on the quality of

teaching and, most importantly, on the training of highly qualified defenders in Uzbekistan. Criteria for selection of teachers in military and special subjects have not been developed. The personnel policy established at the beginning of the Soviet era limited the professional selection and training of teachers for military schools. However, the university did not have special educational institutions to train officers for pedagogical activities forcing the departments to organize their own training sessions, which are usually organized in studying the content of the subjects taught. The efforts of individual pedagogical teams of departments aimed at ensuring the process of professional formation of teachers of higher military educational institutions are often not provided from an eclectic, inconsistent and optimistic point of view. Beginner teachers learn teaching methods by observing the work of more experienced colleagues. Obviously, not all departments are able to prepare teachers at a high level for continuous complex training at the university. As a result of insufficient approach to the organization of the pedagogical process aimed at solving the problem of training and development of teachers, as a result of inconsistencies in the efforts of pedagogical teams of departments to form pedagogical skills, teachers of military universities do not always succeed. they are In the last few years, there has been a declining trend in the level of pedagogical skills of even university teachers.

Military service is a special federal service of citizens in the Armed Forces aimed at protecting the homeland from aggression. The legal framework of military service is based on the Constitution of Uzbekistan, the laws "On Defence", "On Military Service

and Military Service", "On the Status of Military Servicemen", military regulations and other laws of Uzbekistan determined by law. A law is a normative document that regulates the most important social relations, adopted by the supreme body of state power or at the direct request of the population (for example, through a referendum) in the manner prescribed by the Constitution of Uzbekistan. Law and order is a society that arises as a result of the implementation of various social norms that regulate various spheres of public life and are characterized by characteristic and inappropriate ways of influencing people's behaviour (customs, moral norms, etc.). Wars and armed conflicts involve many people who need to be managed and a variety of logistical tools are used that must be used as effectively as possible. The only way to unite these people in accordance with the requirement of armed struggle is to establish a certain order, a rule of their conduct. The primacy of military law contributes to the unification of the military community, strengthening the moral and spiritual condition of the personnel. Any serviceman, his or her colleagues engaged in other activities, must be sure that each of them is in his place, working with him in a strictly prescribed manner.

A military leader, the legal task of military vocational education is not only to provide students with the necessary amount of knowledge or acquire certain practical skills, but also to protect their homeland from aggressors with an inner confidence and responsibility to develop their military-professional knowledge. is also to feed them to perfection. To this end, it is necessary to use guidelines for the effective use of more advanced teaching methods based on the active rejuvenation of

students' learning activities. Traditional methods of practical training in the "story-demonstration-practice" scheme do not ensure that all the basic psychological conditions based on highly effective methods of training students are met. Practice shows that in addition to improving the quality and effectiveness of student preparation, the introduction of new methods in the learning process, a deeper educational impact on students also ensures the effective preparation of students. An important aspect of improving the educational process is to bring the theoretical principles of military work as close as possible to the practical activities of the army. Therefore, it is necessary to create conditions in the educational process that correspond to the real combat environment.

Further reforms in the country have led to significant changes in the Armed Forces of the Republic. For example, the new version of the Law on General Conscription and Military Service was adopted on December 12, 2002. According to it, the law consists of compulsory military training of citizens for the defence of the Republic of Uzbekistan and is introduced in order to replenish the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan and ensure their reserve. The general military obligation is to prepare citizens for military service, conscription (entry).), conscription or contract military service, reserve service, alternative service, observance of military registration rules, measures to protect the population in case of emergency or aggression against the Republic of Uzbekistan. The rights of a serviceman and the procedure for their use shall be established by the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan. No one has the right to restrict the rights of a serviceman guaranteed by the Constitution and laws of

the Republic of Uzbekistan. The use of the rights of servicemen must not infringe on the rights and legitimate interests of society, the state, military service, the rights of other servicemen and various citizens. The state guarantees social and legal protection of servicemen, creating adequate and decent living standards, improving service and living conditions. will take measures to Ensuring and protecting the rights of servicemen is the responsibility of state authorities and local self-government bodies, courts, military administrations and commanders (chiefs) of law enforcement agencies. In particular, conscription in the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan, The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan and other laws and military regulations provide full benefits. Soldiers-sailors, sergeants-sergeants, officers serving in the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan enjoy the right to participate in the parliament, local elections, referendums and other issues.

A serviceman is a person who performs active military service. He is a defender of the Motherland, the independent Republic of Uzbekistan. In the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan, servicemen are divided into soldiers and sailors, sergeants and officers (junior, senior, senior). A serviceman has personal responsibility in the process of defending his homeland. Servicemen of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan shall comply with the requirements of the law, military regulations and shall not be involved in the activities of other public organizations and associations pursuing political goals.

The serviceman has the following:

To honourably justify the high title of "Defender" of the Republic of Uzbekistan, to honour the honour and combat glory of

the Armed Forces, its military unit, the prestige of its military rank, to remain faithful to the military oath, to selflessly serve the people. to defend the state independence and territorial integrity of the Republic of Uzbekistan with courage, skill, until the last drop of blood, even without sacrificing his life, to perform military duty; to comply with the requirements of the Constitution of the country, military regulations; To endure the hardships of military service related to the defence of the Republic of Uzbekistan; to acquire regular military professional knowledge, to improve their military training skills; knowledge of the weapons and military equipment entrusted to him, keeping them in constant readiness for use, protection of military property; to be honest, disciplined, courageous, to show reasonable initiative in the performance of military duty; unconditional obedience to commanders (chiefs) and their protection in battle, guarding the battle flag of a military unit; to observe the rules of military etiquette and to perform military salutes, to dress modestly and neatly, to show patriotism, to appreciate the international friendship of peoples, and to strengthen the brotherhood between nations and provinces.

In short, the most important thing is that in the minds of our people there have been great changes in the education system, and the desire and interest in education among our youth is growing. Today, our talented young people are mastering complex technologies in the new, most modern industries of our country, achieving great achievements in science, culture and sports. This is the result of the fact that the head of our state and government have kept pace with the times, paid special attention to the

education system and paid special attention to the process of large-scale education reforms. After all, the present and future of any country is determined, in

fact, by the level of development of the education system, the conditions created for the upbringing of the younger generation.

References:

1. General Military Regulations of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan . T.: Uzbekistan. 1996.
2. G.M. Tansiqboyeva- "International humanitarian law". 2000.
3. F.A. Abdullayev, E.X. Rasulev, A.R. Rakhmonov-"The right to armed conflict. Adolat. 2001.
4. O'.Hakimov. "International humanitarian law". Study guide.Gafur Gulam Publishing House of Literature and Art. 2001.
5. I.K. Abdukarimov. "I will be a general". Cholpon, 2001.
6. "Homeland Defence is a sacred duty". «Uzbekistan», 2001.
7. General military regulations of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan.
8. Regulations on the procedure for military service of citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Tashkent . 2006.
9. Ataboeva Zulfiya-Patriotic values in teenagers social psychological characteristics of formation. Andijan – 2014.

